

STRANDS OF POST-COLONIAL NARRATIVES: CULTURAL FRAGMENTATION THROUGH THE LENS OF NATIVE (JUDITH WRIGHT'S *BORA RING*) AND SETTLER (JHUMPA LAHIRI'S *THE NAMESAKE*) LITERATURE

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Abstract: Post-colonial literature encompasses a vast array of experiences of people from former colonies and is often clubbed together under postcolonialism and commonwealth literature. But a distinction needs to be made in the different forms and diverse exploits, encounters each of these nations and groups of people were exposed to during colonial imperialism. Through a comparative analysis of Judith Wright's *Bora Ring* and Jhumpa Lahiri's *The Namesake*, this paper tries to trace the various strands of cultural fragmentation being experienced by the native and the settler migratory diaspora in post-colonial nations which is subsequently reflected in divergent post-colonial literature forms.

Keywords: Post-colonial literature, commonwealth, cultural fragmentation, native, settler migratory diaspora

Introduction

On a basic terminology, post-colonial literature includes literature from former colonial nations as well as works that are about the practice and legacy of colonialism and the postcolonial experience of the descendants of the colonised. Postcolonialism is concerned with the decolonization of both postcolonial states and Western ones as well, from the political condition to the cultural one. It consists of contesting the contemporary legacies of historical colonialism and breaking the present imbalances of power. Postcolonialism also seeks to criticize contemporary colonial ways by seeking powerful substantial change in postcolonial nations while celebrating the lost history of resistance as well. Narratives of post-colonial literature have various strands- native, settler, diasporic, hyphenated etc which

explore the colonial experience and its aftermath effects delineating themes such as deracination, disjuncture, reclamation of lost culture, oppression, loss of national, cultural and indigenous identity, cultural fragmentation, hybridity, mimicry, dethroning the otherization and subalternity, humanising the colonised etc, but, from diverse perspectives. My paper tries to analyse cultural fragmentation from two lenses- that of the native and the settler/ diaspora by drawing comparison between Judith Wright's poem 'Bora Ring' and Jhumpa Lahiri's novel 'The Namesake' respectively.

Colonialism had and has various facets and consequently the type of native post-colonial literature that arose or was written in different regions are disparate. Native literature stemming from settler colonialism sketch the threads of cultural fragmentation, loss of indigenous culture and identity, attempt to reclaim the lost heritage apart from the oppression, slavery subjugated on the natives. It was perpetuated through the genocide and repression of indigenous peoples and cultures. Essentially hegemonic in scope, settler colonialism normalized the continuous settler occupation, exploiting lands and resources to which indigenous peoples have genealogical relationships. In other words, settler colonizers did not merely exploit indigenous peoples and lands for labour and economic interests; they displaced them through settlements. In contrast, when we examine diasporic or settler or migrant post-colonial literary works, the themes of hyphenated identity, survival, alienation, physical and emotional confrontation with new land along with cultural fragmentation are conspicuous and prominent.

Methodology

Qualitative analysis of the two primary works- *Bora Ring* and *The Namesake* has been adopted along with deconstruction as research methodology. In-depth deconstruction of the narratives of both the literary works have been conducted and some postulates of the theories of post-colonialism, feminism, culture studies have been applied to reach conclusive findings regarding the difference of poetics in the type of colonialism practised and the subsequent difference found in narratives of settler and native post-colonial literature.

Discussion: Tracing Cultural Fragmentation and Loss

One of Australia's most prolific poets, critic and short story writer, Judith Wright was an also an uncompromising environmentalist campaigning for Aboriginal land rights. Wright's one of the best-known poems "Bora Ring" is about a speaker's lamentation on the indigenous cultural loss after the European settlement. Since the colonisation of the British, the annihilation of Australia's Bora Rings took place cosmically. Urbanization coupled with a disrespect for indigenous values have been responsible for the demise of these cultural sites and values. The poetess' first-hand experiences of the dismal conditions since childhood aided to the intense graphic sincerity in her sympathies. The speaker chiefly highlights the Bora ceremony that was observed by the indigenous people of Australia. This ceremony alongside other cultural activities gradually faded. Whenever she hears about them it seems like an unknown episode from an alien tale though it was ironically part of her own cultural history. Due to the dominance of Europeans, aboriginality slid back under the passage of time. They impregnated their culture into the indigenous people and wiped their values away.

The poem begins with the expression of deep anguish and agony at the extermination of the ethnicity of the native Australians which was destroyed by the Europeans. The persona pines for the lost dance of the aborigines. The speaker heartily thinks about the past with a deep scar on his/her mind. In this poem, the speaker illustrates how cultural songs cannot be heard anymore. The aboriginal dance at Corroboree and Bora ceremonies is now history. She sadly describes the current condition with particular emphasis on nature. She infuses life into the grass and apple-gum tree in order to portray how nature laments the loss. The grass, raising their heads above mother earth, marks the sites where the Bora ceremony was performed. Those mounds are now covered with grass as none is there to dance or perform rituals. There are apple gums (a kind of evergreen tree native to Australia) that mime a past corroboree. Corroboree is a traditional dance ceremony of Aboriginal Australians. They painted their bodies with ritualistic colours and danced in the cultural gatherings known as Corroborees. According to the speaker, the nostalgic murmur of leaves resonates with the traditional chants of a Corroboree. Here, the poet uses pathetic fallacy in order to reflect her sense of grief. Not only that, the nomadic tribes who knew no rest are now standing still. Their feet are poised as they are no more. With these ancient people, their culture also went underneath, below the

dust of time. Their story is now an “alien tale” and the trees’ murmur resonates with their “broken chant”. This discord in their cultural history makes the speaker thoughtful. She broods over the aboriginal hunter who once caroused in the forests. Their traditional weapons are splintered and the irresistible feet of nomadic tribes are now still. The aboriginal civilisation is one of hunters and gatherers. Since the advent of the whites, hunting is no more than a dream. All that one discovers of the activities of the native people of Africa is through their broken spears, bows, arrows and boomerangs excavated out by the archaeologists. The cult of painting bodies while dancing, their hunting ethnography; all doomed. The aborigines were forgotten, and so are their memories. The colonisers have rooted out the wellspring and means of all original entertainment: the singing, the dancing, the performances have truncated to isolation.

Throughout the poem, Wright uses vivid imagery and sensory details to evoke a sense of loss and mourning. For example, she describes the “ring of faintest blue” that can still be seen in the grass where the Bora Ring once stood, and the “creek’s healing rushes” that have grown over the “old path” leading to the site. The final stanza of the poem is particularly poignant, as the speaker describes the bora ring as “empty” and “silent.” The sense of absence and loss is palpable, as the speaker mourns for a culture that has been destroyed and for the people who once lived and thrived in this place. In the final stanza, Wright shifts from describing the physical landscape to reflecting on the deeper cultural significance of the Bora Ring. She writes, “Who will dance there now? No one.” This line suggests that the loss of the Bora Ring is not just a physical loss, but a loss of tradition, community, and cultural identity. The poem also uses repetition and parallel structure to reinforce its elegiac tone. The opening lines repeat the phrase “The song is gone” three times, emphasizing the finality of the loss. The line “a dream the world breathed sleeping and forgot” highlights the former prosperity of Australian culture. Personification is used to represent the period before British colonisation of Australia and colonisation in general as in the world was in a peaceful slumber, dreaming, until it woke up, The personification also goes hand in hand with “a dream” because it’s metaphoric for aboriginal culture, the world was dreaming and Aboriginal culture was thriving. European colonisation and specifically for Australia, British ended all the successful cultures prior to contact and colonisation, reflected in the personification for the world dreaming. “Only the rider’s heart halts at a sightless shadow” implies that the continuation of Australian Aboriginal culture has come to a standstill.

In the last stanza of “Bora Ring,” Wright again creates a contrast as she had created in the second stanza. Here, she shows a rider, probably the speaker. The rider can also be a metaphorical representation of the poet. She rides through her cultural past and halts near the sites where once indigenous people gathered. Her cultural past is like a “sightless shadow.” A shadow that cannot be seen. It is formless as if at any point it did not exist. A word rings heavy in her heart. It can be “violence,” “evil,” “murder,” or anything hearing which one’s heart goes numb. This word is related to the “ancient curse” of the biblical character, Cain. He was the first human-born sinner. It is believed that the chain of vices began with this ancient act of violence. By referring to this biblical symbol of evil, the poet somehow tries to justify the point that what happened with her people was destined to happen. But, her heart bubbles in anger, anguish, and angst for those whose cruel sickles dislodged the innocent men from their roots and snapped their cultural shoots.

On the other hand, Jhumpa Lahiri’s novel *The Namesake* deals with the tribulations of the immigrants in an alien land, the yearnings of exile and the emotional bafflement of cross-cultural dilemmas. The novel continues to develop further the themes of cultural alienation and loss of identity. She tries to incarcerate the experiences and cultural dilemmas of the 30-year struggle of the Ganguli family, for their integration and assimilation into an alien culture. Lahiri’s protagonists are the continental immigrants but they endure cultural introspection. They have their conflict of consciousness between two selves- the native and the foreign.

The novel begins with the pathetic depiction of apprehension, clumsiness and an assortment of psychosociological problems such as longing, rootlessness, estrangement, schizophrenia experienced by Ashima, who at a young age has migrated to a country where "she is related to no one". Motherliness for Ashima does not bring only cheerfulness but also the menace of raising the child all alone in country of strangers. The child's birth was a lonesome celebration and the realization that his entry in the world was, “unaccompanied and deprived” laid the foundation of that predicament that small child had to experience throughout his life. Ashima's struggle to adjust in a foreign country, to become accustomed herself to the newly found atmosphere is the struggle of every immigrant who expose their self- identity in an alien land. Feeling lonely and displaced in a foreign land, Ashima begins to feel that: “Being

a foreigner is a sort of life-long pregnancy-A Perpetual wait, a constant burden, a continuous feeling out of sorts.” She starts accepting the American ways of living but longing for her home country in her is kept intact by adhering to the Indian traditions and rituals. Ashok and Ashima create a sense of Indianness for themselves, by getting them familiar with all the Bengali families living around. She also maintains address books in which she has recorded the names and address of every Indian whom she comes across. She prides herself on each entry and feels fortunate to "have the fortune to share rice with them in a foreign land". Her discomfort with the life around her represents the incomprehensible world of American immigrants who are born in one country but squander their life either gracefully engrossed or completely drowning in the civilization of another people.

The anxiety, the fear of losing one's identity in an entirely foreign land, is passed on to the next generation also. Ashok and Ashima's son Gogol, who emerges as the central figure in the novel is the typical example of this phenomenon. He inherits not only his parent's way of life or looks, but also inherits the same pain of being lost in the midst of an alien culture. Gogol is discontented with his name and hates it for lacking self-respect or enormity. A name is an introductory ID tag to the world but Gogol, when he is in his teens despises his name so much so that "he came to hate questions pertaining to his name, hates having constantly to explain. He hates having to tell people that it does not mean anything in Indian. He hates that his name is both silly and difficult to understand, that it has nothing to do with who he is, that he is neither Indian nor American but of all things Russian.” In fact, the title, ‘The Namesake’ reflects the struggle Gogol Ganguli goes through to identity with his unusual name. His struggle for establishing his individuality is twofold. The name that ultimately defines a person's individuality becomes a burden for him. It does not give him an identity but puts him in a dilemma, regarding his original identity. Secondly, as a child of immigrants in America, he persistently has to fight with conflicts arising due to his sense belongings and loss of identity.

Gogol who hates his name, for the first time in his life, takes an independent choice and decides to get it changed Nikhil. It is as Nikhil, Gogol faces the predicament of establishing his real identity. He finds it complicated to acknowledge that Gogol and Nikhil are both a part of his own individual self and torn between this struggle he feels as “if he's cast himself in a

play acting the part of twins, indistinguishable to the naked eye, yet fundamentally different.” He is having two aspects regarding his change of name – Gogol, the son of Indian parents behave and act according to Indian culture and values; Nikhil on the other hand, is the free openminded person, who has left his past behind and has nothing to do with Gogol. It is as Nikhil that Gogol forgets all the cultural restrictions imposed on him by his parents, who even after spending twenty years in America cannot bring themselves to refer to Pemberton Road as home. His parents can never reject their old cultural ethics and one can sense the presence of deep-rooted reminiscence in their behavior. Gogol and Sonia view their multi-cultural life differently. Though there are required to sit in pujas and other religious ceremonies, Gogol and Sonia like the children to their Bengali families take pleasure in American food more than the Bengali dishes. The parents admit to their children’s wishes. The Gangulis, too, incorporate the American way of living into their lives for their sake of children: they learn to roast turkeys on thanksgiving, to nail a wreath to their door in December, to wrap woollen scarves around snowman, to colour boiled eggs violet and pink at Easter for the sake of Gogol and Sonia they celebrate with progressively increasing fanfare the birth of Christ an event the children look forward to far more than the worship of Durga and Saraswati . After their visit to Calcutta once in a year, they crave to go back to their western ways.

He manages to have a dual existence - an existence having both Indian and American cultural values. Gogol represents the Indian part in him where as Nikhil is the embodiment of all the cultural values that America has given to Gogol. It is while living these two lives, that Gogol realizes the need of an identity, which is not based on his roots. The predicament that Gogol experiences is the symbol of that wretchedness which every immigrant experiences when he has to respond any query based on his identity. Though he is born and brought up in America yet to Americans he is still an Indian. When he comes back to the country of his father, he is referred as an NRI. The feeling of sense of belongingness, the urge to be claimed by one's root is universal and perhaps it is the only reason that a person ultimately returns to the country of this birth. The pain, the torment, the lack of ability to adjust to foreign surrounding, compels the immigrants to long for their own country where their own people surround them. But in the "The Namesake", Lahiri had movingly portrayed the ache of the next generation, who has no land, to be called as their own. They are living in a land, which they 'own' by birth, but does not “belong to the land” because of their fragmented identity.

Gogol want to be liberated from his Indian backgrounds but after his father's death, the Indian values which he had inherited, from him, makes him move closer to his mother and his sister resulting in a strain with his relationship with his girlfriend Maxine. The sudden death of his father makes him turn back towards his family and unknowingly he donned the responsibility of an elder son, as he would have done if he had lived in India. Gogol's quest for identity is a never -ending search; he cannot reject the Indian culture and cannot even fully accept the American values. This turns out to be on going, draining and difficult process for him. He cannot reject the demands of tradition and cannot afford to accommodate to the temptations offered by a new culture. He belongs to postmodern world which is defined as "the age of refuge" and modern man as "the new nomad" not being able to put down roots anywhere.

Stuart Hall, in his essay, "Cultural Identity and Diaspora" says that identity is not as transparent and unproblematic as we think it to be. Instead of thinking of identity as an already accomplished fact, we should think of it as a product, which is never complete, and is always in process, always constituted within, not outside, representation. Hall defines "cultural identity" to be a matter of "becoming" as well as "being". But, like everything that is historical, they undergo constant transformation. The first generation Gangulis over the time maintained a balance between two cultures, but the younger generation could not locate their identity in either of the two home-host cultures. They instead inculcate those cultural customs which go beyond nation, history, space and time.

Conclusion

Thus, by examining both the works, we can observe the marked difference in use of language, treatment of themes, imagery and other literary devices employed to bifurcate the divergence or polarity in experiences of the native and settler/diasporic colonial and postcolonial experiences. *Bora Ring* delineates the loss of the indigenous identity and the cultural hierarchy imposed by the colonisers, is an attempt to reclaim that lost heritage through recalling the glorious past whereas, *The Namesake* depicts the constant struggle for survival, search for an identity that's already dislocated and the cultural fragmentation of

Indian diaspora- establishing the disparate strands of post-colonial narratives, which are often considered in a misplaced manner under the same umbrella.

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